

DELIVERABLE REPORT

VALIDATION OF ACF FOR LARGE AND SMALL PITCH ASSEMBLIES

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Abstract:

A flexible, reliable and cost-effective interconnect technology is required for the development of hybrid pixel detectors, which is suitable for in-house single-die hybridisation performed during the R&D phase. Within WP6, an in-house single-die interconnect process based on Anisotropic Conductive Adhesives (ACA) has been developed and validated with dedicated interconnect test structures and a variety of different ASICs and sensors. The ACA interconnect technology replaces solder bumps with conductive micro-particles embedded in an epoxy layer applied as either film (ACF) or paste (ACP). The electro-mechanical connection between the sensor and ASIC is achieved via thermocompression of the ACA using a flip-chip device bonder. The ACA technology requires metal pads with a vertical extension above the passivation layer, which is achieved using a newly developed in-house single-die Electroless Nickel Immersion Gold (ENIG) bump-deposition process. This document reports on the achieved validation of the developed plating and interconnect processes for pad diameters ranging from 12 μm to 140 μm and pitches between 20 μm and 1.3 mm.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2025

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Delivery Slip

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A single-die in-house pixel-detector hybridisation process based on Anisotropic Conductive Films (ACF) with embedded conductive micro-particle has been developed. It provides a cost-effective and flexible alternative to standard bump-bonding processes, which are only available in specialised industries and require full-wafer processing. An in-house mask-less ENIG plating process for bumping of aluminium pads on fine-pitch ASICs and sensors has been developed within the project scope to support the hybridisation activities. It has been optimised using dedicated connectivity-test chain devices produced at FBK (Trento). The ACF hybridisation process has been developed and characterized, using the connectivity test devices and the bumps from the developed ENIG process. An interconnect yield of 97% has been achieved for pixel pitches down to 55 μm and a bonding area up to 2 cm^2 . First reliability tests show a good robustness against thermal stress. Preliminary results from tests performed in the collaborating projects on functional proof-of-concept fine-pitch ACF hybrid assemblies show interconnect yields up to 85% on small-area devices ($<10 \text{ mm}^2$) at a pitch down to 55 μm .

2. INTRODUCTION

Building reliable, high-performance, large-area tracking and timing detector systems with minimal material content and at an affordable cost presents major challenges that future experiments will have to face. The detector-integration challenges include hybridizing pixel sensors and readout ASICs with various pitches. Moreover, during the R&D phase, the hybridisation often needs to be performed on single-die level, while most industrial interconnect processes require full-wafers processing.

Within AIDAinnova WP6, the use of Anisotropic Conductive Adhesives (ACA) is studied for single-die in-house flip-chip pixel-detector hybridisation as a cost-effective and flexible alternative to standard bump-bonding processes [1-3]. The ACA technology is adapted from industry, where it is commonly used for interconnection at the periphery of LCDs. Both, film-based (ACF) and paste-based (ACP) adhesives with embedded conductive micro-particles are investigated, as shown schematically in Figure 1. The ACA technology can also be used for ASIC-PCB/FPC integration, replacing wire bonding or large-pitch solder bumping techniques.

The considered adhesive-based hybridisation technologies require a specific topology of the metal-pad contacts on the pixels, to create direct contact between the pads and the micro-particles as well as sufficient cavity volume for the excess adhesive (see Figure 1). The project has therefore developed Electroless Nickel Immersion Gold (ENIG) plating as a versatile in-house process that can achieve uniform plating onto aluminium electrodes for various target applications [2, 3].

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the ACF flip-chip hybridisation process.

For simplified validation of the plating and interconnect processes under study, the project has designed and produced dedicated daisy-chain test devices mimicking the geometry of the various target applications (as documented in the AidaInnova MS 24, [4]).

This report briefly introduces the daisy-chain test devices in section 3, before presenting validation results of the plating (section 4) and ACF interconnect (section 5) processes. The final section 0 presents conclusions and an outlook to future work.

3. CHAIN-DEVICE TEST STRUCTURES

Dedicated daisy-chain devices for plating and interconnect tests have been produced by FBK (Trento). The devices are implemented as pairs mimicking the ASIC and sensor in a hybrid assembly. A single-patterned metal layer is implemented on top of a 6-inch quartz substrate of 625 μm thickness (Figure 2). The layout and thickness of the metal and passivation layer mimics the matrix size, pitch and topology of various target ASICs and sensors (Timepix3 [5], CLICpix2 [6], RD53 [7]). Devices with larger pads and low pad density are also implemented to test flip-chip techniques for module integration. For each pair, the routing between the pads allows for electrical measurements of the connectivity and contact resistance in various configurations after flip chip. Both the global interconnect yield, as well as local yield variations can be probed. A lot of eight wafers have been produced and used for optimising and validating the plating and interconnect processes described in the following sections. More details on the test-structure design and production can be found in the milestone report MS24 [4].

Figure 2: Schematic layout (left) and photo (right) of a 6" daisy-chain wafer produced on a quartz substrate of 625 μm thickness.

4. ENIG PLATING

Adapting electrodes and metal pads for different interconnection methods is crucial for achieving a sufficient bonding quality. A versatile Electroless Nickel Immersion Gold (ENIG) plating process has therefore been developed as an in-house process that can achieve uniform plating onto aluminium electrodes for various target applications [2,3].

The processing consists of 4 main steps: (1) Pre-treatment: application of protective coating on metal areas to be excluded from the plating; plasma activation of samples. (2) Zincation of the aluminum pads. (3) Electroless nickel deposition. (4) Application of thin ($<1 \mu\text{m}$) gold layer for corrosion protection by immersion in a cyanide-based solution.

Recent plating activities have focused on a systematic optimisation of the developed ENIG process towards a standardised process flow (Figure 3 (left)), leading to consistent plating results for a variety of applications.

4.1. BUMP-HEIGHT CALIBRATION

The achieved height of the ENIG bumps as function of nickel-deposition time was observed to be approximately linear within the measured range, corresponding to 10 μm after one hour of deposition (Figure 3 (right)). Slight variations in deposition rates between chips are attributed to differences in pad metallisation purity or deposition techniques.

Figure 3: Left: Example process flow for ENIG plating. Right: Observed height of bumps versus nickel deposition time.

4.2. PLATING RESULTS

The ENIG plating process has been applied and optimised on daisy-chain test structures with different pitches and matrix sizes (Figure 4), as well as on functional sensor and ASIC samples from various projects (Figure 5).

An excellent plating yield >99% has been achieved for all types of samples with matrix areas up to approximately 2 cm^2 , reaching 100% in areas without contamination issues observed prior to plating. No missing bumps and no overplating were observed with the optimised plating process. A bump height up to approximately 10 μm and a uniformity of better than $\pm 1 \mu\text{m}$ are achieved.

The results have been found to be reproducible across repeated platings applied on the same device types. The parameters of all tested samples and the achieved ENIG plating results are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 4: Left: Microscope picture of plating on Timepix3-type daisy chain device with 55 μm pitch and 14 x 14 mm^2 matrix size. Right: Optical profilometry after plating on a small-pitch test structure with 20 μm pitch and 3.2 x 3.2 mm^2 matrix size.

Figure 5: Left: Microscope picture showing uniform ENIG plating across the pixel matrix of a functional ColorPix2 ASIC with 70 μm pitch. The periphery pads on the lower part of the ASIC are protected with a locally applied removable protective coating. Right: SEM pictures of ENIG plating on a functional SiGe readout ASIC (top) and an AC-LGAD sensor from KEK (bottom).

Table 1: Parameters of different samples and achieved ENIG plating results.

Sample	Chip size	Pad diameter	Pitch	ENIG height
“Timepix3” daisy-chain test structures	14 x 14 mm ²	12-22 μm	55 μm	10 $\mu\text{m} \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$
“Small pitch” daisy-chain test structures	3.2 x 3.2 mm ²	10 x 8 μm^2 (rectang.)	20 μm	4.5 $\mu\text{m} \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$
Timespot1 ASIC	2.4 x 2.7 mm ²	19 μm	55 μm	10 $\mu\text{m} \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$
SPHIRD silicon sensor	1.6 x 3.2 mm ²	19 μm	50 μm	5-6 μm
ATLAS HGTD LGAD sensors	20 x 22 mm ²	90 μm	1.3 mm	8.5 $\mu\text{m} \pm 0.7 \mu\text{m}$
SiGe ASICs and KEK AC-LGAD sensors	A: 1.3 x 2.9 mm ² S: 1.9 x 1.9 mm ²	40 μm	100 μm	8.5 $\mu\text{m} \pm 0.6 \mu\text{m}$
ColorPix2	3 x 4.9 mm ²	40 μm	70 μm	11 $\mu\text{m} \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$

5. ACF HYBRIDISATION

The developed ACF hybridisation process is shown schematically in Figure 6 (left) for the example of an ASIC-to-sensor interconnection. An ACF material with a thickness of 18 μm and gold-coated micro-particles of 3 μm in diameter embedded with a density of 71'000 particles / mm² is used for all ACF bonding results described in the following sections. In preparation for the bonding, the ACF material is cut to shape and laminated to the ASIC using low heat (90 °C) and low pressure (approximately 1 MPa) for 5 seconds, followed by a cool-down phase of 4-5 minutes. For the actual bonding, the ASIC and sensor are aligned in the flip-chip bonder, and thermocompression with up to 160 °C and 100 kgf is applied for a few seconds to bring the pads on both sides into direct contact with the conductive micro-particles and cure the glue. The high force is kept during the cool-down phase of 5-10 minutes. A successful bonding result requires the excess glue to be contained in the

cavity volume around the exposed pads and the conductive particles to be slightly deformed, as shown in Figure 6 (right) for a Timepix3 ASIC hybridised to a planar sensor.

Figure 6: Left: Schematic representation of ACF lamination and flip-chip bonding process. Right: Cross-section through hybrid ACF assembly of Timepix3 ASIC (bottom) with planar silicon sensor (top), showing contact between the ENIG pads through deformed conductive micro particles.

5.1. ACF HYBRIDISATION OF DAISY-CHAIN TEST DEVICES

The daisy-chain test devices introduced in section 3 have been used to produce ACF-bonded samples that were tested with electrical connectivity measurements to confirm the obtained interconnect yield. Figure 7 shows a 15 mm x 16 mm large "SubTimepix3" daisy-chain hybrid, which has been assembled and electrically tested. This assembly mimics the geometry of a Timepix3 hybrid sensor assembly, featuring rectangular pads measuring 22 µm per side on one chip ("sensor") and 12 µm per side on the other ("ASIC"), with a pitch of 55 µm. The matrix contains 256 × 256 pads and includes 72 chain structures, each consisting of 28 connections in series.

Figure 7: "Sub-Timepix" daisy-chain assembly after ACF hybridisation. The electrical connection scheme of the daisy chain is shown on the right.

Bumps were placed on both sides using an earlier version of the in-house ENIG process described above. The plating was excellent on one chip but imperfect on the other, with smaller bumps observed at the matrix edges. The bump heights were approximately 10 µm on one chip and 9 µm on the other. The bonding was performed with a force of 100 kgf.

Electrical tests were conducted on the 72 chains using a probe station. The resistance of each chain was measured with the 4-wire method. For fully connected chains, the measured resistance values are dominated by the resistance of the lines connecting the islands to the periphery. Disconnected pads, on the other hand, result in open connections for the entire chain. The measurements revealed that 29 chains were properly connected, corresponding to 40% of the 72 chains. Based on this data, the probability p of a pad being correctly connected is estimated as: $p^{28} = 29/72$, $p = 96.8\%$.

An assembly with uniform plating on a Timepix3 ASIC [5] with a matrix of 256 x 256 pixels at 55 μm pitch and a 300 μm thick planar sensor has been bonded at 100 kgf with full coverage of the ACF and then evaluated in a beam test at different detection thresholds. The size of the matrix, along with the small pixel pitch, result in a build-up of excess adhesive in the centre of the bonded chip, while the excess adhesive near the 4 sides can flow out of the bonding area. Therefore, the edges of the ASIC show good interconnection yield with a high tracking efficiency achieved even at high detection thresholds, compared to weakly connected regions in the centre, as shown in Figure 9. A further increase of the plating height or a flip-chip bonder with a higher maximum bonding pressure are expected to yield an improved connection yield.

Figure 9: Reconstruction efficiency for high-momentum particle tracks passing through an ACF-bonded Timepix3 assembly for low (left) and high (right) detection thresholds. The reduced efficiency visible at the high detection threshold originates from weak coupling caused by excess of adhesive in the centre.

5.3.2. Hybridisation of SPHIRD ASICs with silicon sensors

Assemblies of SPHIRD ASICs [8] provided by ESRF (Grenoble) have been bonded with a Silicon sensor and subsequently tested with a monochromatic X-ray beam at the ESRF. The SPHIRD ASICs contain a matrix of 32 x 64 pixels of 50 μm pitch. The ACF bonded Si assembly showed 85% of pixels with the expected response for a good connection, while about 7 % show a weak response and 7% show no response.

5.3.3. Hybridisation of Timespot1 ASICs with 3D trench silicon sensors

A functional Timespot1 readout ASIC [9] and a 3D trench silicon sensor [10] were hybridized, each containing a 32 x 32 matrix of pixels with a pitch of 55 μm . Bumps with a height of approximately 10 μm were placed on the ASIC using an earlier version of the in-house ENIG process described above. The ENIG processing yielded imperfect results, as this was the first chip of this type processed, leading to variations in bump size of $\pm 1 \mu\text{m}$. The sensor contained bare aluminium pads without plating.

The produced hybrid was then wire-bonded to a readout board (Figure 10) and characterized with a Sr-90 beta source.

Figure 10: Timespot1 assembly before (left) and after (right) wire bonding.

The interconnect yield was estimated from the observed hit rates per pixel, after applying a noise cut on the Time-over-Threshold (ToT) pulse-height measurement. Unstable data-taking conditions with randomly appearing unresponsive pixels required frequent reprogramming of the chip, which limits the achievable coverage. The observed hit pattern over the matrix indicates a uniform source illumination and no local accumulation of unresponsive pixels (Figure 11 (left)). A lower limit on the interconnect yield was placed at 85.5%, corresponding to the fraction of pixels with at least 5 hits above the ToT threshold of 3 ns accumulated over several acquisition runs (Figure 11 (right)).

Figure 11: Left: Number of hits observed across the Timespot1 matrix during Sr-90 exposition. Right: Bonding efficiency (fraction of responding pixels) as a function of the cut on the minimum number of pixel hits requested to be counted as responding. For both plots, a noise cut on the ToT value of 3 ns is applied. (From [11].)

6. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The mask-less in-house single-die ENIG plating process developed within the project scope has been optimised for high and uniform bump height, using dedicated connectivity test structures. An innovative in-house flip-chip hybridisation technique based on films with embedded conductive microparticles and on ENIG bumps has been developed and characterized, using the connectivity test structures. An interconnect yield of 97% has been achieved for pixel pitches down to 55 μm and a bonding area up to 2 cm^2 . First reliability tests show a good robustness against thermal stress. Preliminary test results from various functional proof-of-concept fine-pitch hybrid assemblies show interconnect yields up to 85% on small-area devices ($< \sim 10 \text{ mm}^2$). For large-area fine-pitch devices ($> 100 \text{ mm}^2$), the interconnect yield achieved up to now is limited by the plating height and bonding force.

The in-house plating and ACF interconnect processes developed in the framework of AIDAinnova enable new hybrid-detector R&D projects based on this technology. They will be further studied and optimized within the Interconnect Working Group (WG7) of the DRD3 collaboration on solid-state detector R&D [12].

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8. ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
ACA	Anisotropic Conductive Adhesive
ACF	Anisotropic Conductive Film
ACP	Anisotropic Conductive Paste
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
LCD	Liquid-Crystal Display
ENIG	Electroless Nickel Immersion Gold